

December 16, 2024

Press release

On 11 December 2024, DLR, in collaboration with the CST4ALL consortium, hosted a successful online workshop on R&I Meteorology for Renewable Energy Technologies.

The workshop was attended by over 90 participants from research, industry and governmental organisations. The two sessions covered key research areas in meteorology for concentrated solar thermal, photovoltaics and wind energy.

Philippe Schild (European Commission, DG for Research and Innovation) welcomed the participants and thanked them for taking part in the event and for their willingness to work together. He emphasised the importance of competitiveness in the EU in relation to energy and resources. He acknowledged the significant role of meteorology, for example in optimizing site selection. Circularity and climate change are key topics in the EU, and in this context, he believes that meteorology research can support the development of more resilient energy systems.

Peter Heller (DLR, Germany) as coordinator of the CST4All project gave a short overview on the project followed by moderating two technical sessions. The first one included presentations from Alberto Troccoli (Managing Director at World Energy & Meteorology Council, CEO at Inside Climate Service srl & Visiting Professor at the University of East Anglia (UK)) on the topic of “The state of the art of meteorology for solar technologies and further renewable energy systems”, Manuel Silva (*Professor and Researcher at University of Seville, Task Manager at SolarPACES Task V*) on “Ongoing long-standing research” and Andrea N. Hahmann (DTU Senior Scientist, Department of Wind and Energy Systems) presented on the topic of “Current meteorological research for wind energy resources”.

The second technical session comprised presentations from Corinna Möhrle (WEPROG Managing Director) on the subject of “Wind resource assessment, monitoring and forecasting” and Jan Remund (Meteotest Head of Business Unit Energy and Climatology, Task Manager IEA PVPS Task 16) on the subject of “Solar resource assessment, monitoring and forecasting”.

A poll was conducted among the audience, which revealed the crucial role of meteorological research in achieving firm power. The investigation of the effects of the so-called “Dunkelflaute”, climate change, and extreme weather risks were identified as key areas of focus.

The poll also revealed a discrepancy between research and application, with the appropriate selection of meteorological data sets among the various available data types identified as a challenge. A number of solutions are currently being developed, including the IEA Wind [Recommended Practices](#), which assist in identifying the most appropriate wind forecast for a specific application. Another example that helps to overcome this gap is the IEA [Best Practices Handbook for the Collection and Use of Solar Resource Data for Solar Energy Applications](#).

The key points to draw from the workshop are as follows:

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- There is a need for accurate and low-cost weather data
- Historical forecast and future projection data are also required
- Work is needed to improve data harmonisation and data quality
- High penetration of renewable power can lead to challenges in the grid
- There are many meteorological models that are useful for research and industry
- Best practices and user guidelines are essential in this field.

CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas,
Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo
sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications
(TR)

The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow-us on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
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You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

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